
Do Firm Characteristics Explain Stock Returns under The Scaled CAPM? Evidence from the Egyptian Stock Market

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Abstract

This paper examines whether the size and value anomalies in the Egyptian stock market can be explained as compensation for time-varying systematic risk within a scaled conditional CAPM framework. Using monthly data for 128 non-financial firms listed on the Egyptian stock exchange (EGX) over 2009–2024, this study interacts the market factor with lagged conditioning variables, the Treasury bill rate, firm size, and book-to-market ratio, and tests whether risk-adjusted returns retain significant characteristic-based predictability in Fama–MacBeth cross-sectional regressions with Newey–West standard errors. Three main findings are reported: first, a strong value premium exists in raw returns and persists across all scaled specifications, indicating that a single-factor conditional model cannot fully rationalize the value anomaly, second, the size effect is absent in unadjusted returns but becomes statistically significant once the market factor is scaled by the risk-free rate, revealing that macroeconomic interest rate variation masks the firm-size

premium in unscaled models, third, the average adjusted R-squared declines monotonically from 2.42% to 1.75% across increasingly rich specifications, confirming that scaled conditioning absorbs anomaly variation progressively but does not eliminate it. Overall, the results suggest that richer multifactor and conditional frameworks are needed to fully explain cross-sectional return patterns in emerging markets.

Keywords: Scaled CAPM, Conditional asset pricing, Size effect, Value premium, Fama–MacBeth, Egyptian stock exchange, Emerging markets

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1. Introduction

A main challenge in empirical asset pricing is to determine whether observed cross-sectional return patterns reflect genuine compensation for risk or represent unexploited arbitrage opportunities. The size and value effects, the tendency for small-capitalization stocks and high book-to-market stocks to earn higher average returns, have been among the most thoroughly documented anomalies in prior literature since Banz (1981) and Fama and French (1992). While these patterns have been attributed both to rational risk compensation and to behavioral or liquidity-related mispricing, their interpretation remains a fundamental open question, particularly in markets where standard pricing models perform poorly.

The conditional asset pricing literature offers a systematic framework for addressing this question. If size and value effects proxy for exposure to time-varying systematic risk, they should lose statistical significance once market risk is properly measured, conditional on available information. Contributions by Ferson and Harvey (1999), Jagannathan and Wang (1996), and Lettau and Ludvigson (2001) demonstrate that conditioning on economic state variables can substantially reduce mispricing associated with firm characteristics, an influential empirical formalization of this approach is the scaled factor model of Avramov and Chordia (2006), which scales the market factor by lagged conditioning variables to generate time-varying risk exposures, and then tests whether risk-adjusted returns retain significant exposure to characteristic-based anomalies.

Emerging markets provide a particularly challenging setting for these tests. Markets such as the Egyptian Exchange (EGX) are characterized by structural instability, periodic liquidity crises, political shocks, and limited investor base, all of which can generate substantial time variation in risk that may confound unconditional tests. At the same time, the pronounced illiquidity and information asymmetries common to these markets raise the possibility that observed anomalies partly reflect frictions rather than risk factor loadings. Despite this importance, rigorous conditional tests of anomaly pricing in Egyptian equities are rare.

This paper aims to fill this gap by examining whether scaling the CAPM market factor with macroeconomic and firm-level conditioning variables (the Treasury bill rate, firm size, and book-to-market ratio) can explain the size and value anomalies in the Egyptian stock market. Using firm-level monthly data from 2009 to 2024 and the two-pass Fama–MacBeth methodology with Newey–West standard errors, we construct risk-adjusted returns from scaled conditional CAPM time-series regressions and test whether firm characteristics retain predictive power for these adjusted returns.

The paper makes three main contributions. First, it provides the first systematic application of the scaled CAPM framework of Avramov and Chordia (2006) to the Egyptian equity market, extending the limited conditional asset pricing evidence available for this market. Second, it separately identifies the role of macroeconomic conditioning (through the risk-free rate) and firm-level conditioning (through size and book-to-market) in explaining anomaly pricing, yielding novel evidence on their relative importance. Third, it documents that the size effect is latent in unconditional models but is revealed by scaled conditioning that strips out macroeconomic risk, providing new evidence on how risk confounding shapes anomaly detection in emerging markets.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 reviews the theoretical and empirical literature on conditional asset pricing and anomaly explanation, section 3 describes the methodology, including the scaled factor model and Fama–MacBeth estimation, and describes the variables, section 4 describes the data, presents empirical results, and discusses the findings in the context of the existing literature, and section 5 concludes this work.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Asset Pricing Anomalies and the Limits of Static Models

The empirical asset pricing literature documents a rich set of return patterns that cannot be reconciled with the unconditional CAPM. Banz (1981) provides the earliest rigorous evidence of

a size effect, showing that small firms earn excess returns relative to the CAPM prediction after controlling for beta, further Basu (1977) documents that high earnings-to-price stocks outperform low earnings-to-price stocks on a risk-adjusted basis, and Fama and French (1992) provide a comprehensive analysis showing that firm size and book-to-market ratio together capture most of the cross-sectional variation in average stock returns, while market beta has little marginal explanatory power once these characteristics are included.

The Fama–French (1993) three-factor model elevated the size (SMB) and value (HML) factors to the status of systematic risk factors, motivated by the argument that small firms and value firms are exposed to common risk factors associated with financial distress and macroeconomic sensitivity. However, as Fama and French (1996) acknowledge, this interpretation remains empirical: the model lacks a tight theoretical foundation for why size and value should constitute priced risk factors. This ambiguity has sustained a debate between risk-based and behavioral explanations of anomaly pricing, reviewed comprehensively by Cochrane (2008) and Barberis and Thaler (2003).

A key limitation of both the CAPM and the Fama–French model is their unconditional nature as they assume constant risk exposures and constant risk premia. Ferson and Harvey (1999) provide early evidence that beta and the market risk premium vary systematically with the business cycle, implying that unconditional tests mis-specify the true risk return relationship. Jagannathan and Wang (1996) demonstrate that a conditional CAPM incorporating human capital and business cycle variables substantially improves the cross-sectional fit relative to the static model. Lettau and Ludvigson (2001) show that conditioning the consumption-CAPM on the consumption-wealth ratio enables the model to explain the value premium. These contributions establish the theoretical concept that conditioning on appropriate economic state variables can explain a substantial portion of characteristic-based return predictability as rational risk compensation.

2.2 Scaled Factor Models and the Anomaly Explanation Test

The scaled factor model of Avramov and Chordia (2006) provides an elegant and internally consistent framework for testing whether anomalies are explained by conditional risk. Rather than estimating expected returns and risk premia as explicit functions of state variables, which requires strong parametric assumptions. The scaled model scales the market factor directly by lagged conditioning variables and allows beta to vary as a linear function of these variables, this generates a set of scaled factors in the time-series regression, whose residuals represent the component of returns unexplained by conditional market risk. These residuals are then used as

the dependent variable in the second-stage Fama–MacBeth cross-sectional regressions, with firm characteristics as regressors. Under the null hypothesis of correct conditional pricing, firm characteristics should have no additional explanatory power for risk-adjusted returns.

Avramov and Chordia (2006) apply this framework to U.S. equity data using size, book-to-market, leverage, and past returns as conditioning variables, and reporting that conditioning substantially reduces the statistical significance of size and value effects, however, momentum remains unexplained, consistent with the broader literature. Importantly, their specification explicitly separates macroeconomic and firm-level sources of time variation in beta, a decomposition that is central to the present study.

The scaled model has been extended and tested in various international contexts. Bauer, Cosemans, and Schotman (2010) apply the framework to European equity markets and find that conditioning reduces anomaly pricing, but significant cross-sectional predictability remains for value stocks. Cosemans and Schotman (2010) report similar results for European markets, highlighting that the explanatory power of the scaled model depends crucially on the quality and breadth of the conditioning information set. Liu and Huang (2021) extend the analysis to Chinese equities and find that conditional risk accounts for a substantial fraction of value and momentum premia in that market.

A critical benchmark for the scaled model is provided by Lewellen and Nagel (2006), who examine the conditional CAPM using rolling beta estimates and document that conditional alphas for value portfolios are large, stable, and statistically significant. They argue that betas would need to covary with the market risk premium by an implausible magnitude to explain the value premium, concluding that the conditional CAPM fails to explain value anomalies. Their analysis provides a strong prior that simple single-factor conditional models are insufficient, even when beta variation is allowed.

In the context of emerging markets, the evidence on conditional anomaly pricing is limited. Iqbal. et al. (2010) examine Pakistan and find that conditional models provide only modest improvement over unconditional benchmarks. Ho. et al. (2005) document that size effects in Hong Kong are concentrated in bear markets, consistent with state-dependent risk exposure but not fully explained by conditional market risk. Further, in the Middle East and North Africa region, Algebaly (2022) provides evidence for Egypt that conditioning on market states restores a positive market risk–return relation but does not systematically examine the pricing of size and value anomalies within the scaled factor framework.

2.3 Evidence from Egypt and the Role of Market Frictions

The Egyptian stock market is the oldest in the Middle East and Africa, with origins dating to the late nineteenth century, but it has experienced repeated structural disruptions, including the 2008 global financial crisis, the 2011 political revolution, and subsequent episodes of currency devaluation and economic reforms. These events have fundamentally altered the composition of the investor base, market liquidity, and the dynamics of risk and expected returns. Otaify (2020) documents that market activity collapsed sharply following the 2011 revolution, with a large proportion of listed firms becoming effectively inactive, while Algebaly (2022) shows that the market risk premium is significantly positive only in down-market states.

The limited literature on factor pricing in Egypt offers mixed results. Shaker and Elgiziry (2013) find that the Fama–French three-factor model outperforms the CAPM in explaining cross-sectional returns, consistent with evidence from other emerging markets. Abdo (2019) confirms that both size and value factors are priced, with the five-factor model providing marginal improvement over the three-factor specification. Tahaa and Elgiziry (2016) extend the analysis to include liquidity and earnings-to-price and find that size and book-to-market remain significant after these controls. El Abd (2016) finds evidence of a size effect but no significant value premium, a finding that contrasts with more recent evidence and may reflect the specific sample period employed.

In terms of conditional modeling, Omran (2003) provides early evidence of time-varying betas in Egypt and finds that accounting for beta variation improves the explanatory power of the CAPM. Abdo (2019) applies the Fama–MacBeth methodology with rolling betas and finds that firm characteristics, including size and value, retain predictive power after risk adjustment. These studies establish that conditional market risk is relevant in Egypt but fall short of a comprehensive scaled-factor examination of anomaly pricing where the present study directly addresses this gap.

3. Research Methodology

This section describes the econometric framework used to test whether systematic risk factors are priced in the Egyptian stock market and whether conditional versions of the CAPM can explain observed return anomalies, specifically the size and value effects. The analysis combines two complementary approaches: time-series regressions, which estimate each stock's sensitivity to systematic risk factors, and Fama–MacBeth cross-sectional regressions, which test whether higher risk exposures translate into higher average returns. Special emphasis is placed on methods that allow risk to vary over time, including rolling-window beta estimation and scaled

factor models, to assess whether capturing this time variation improves the model's explanatory power.

This section presents descriptive statistics for the key variables employed in testing whether size- and value-related return patterns in the Egyptian stock market can be explained by time-varying systematic risk within a scaled conditional CAPM framework. The variables examined include individual stock excess returns, the market risk premium, firm size, book-to-market ratio, and the risk-free rate, which together form the conditioning and outcome variables used in the scaled factor specifications.

3.1 Variables Description

This study employs a set of firm-specific characteristics and market-wide variables to estimate the Conditional Capital Asset Pricing Model (Conditional CAPM) and examine the pricing of systematic risk in the Egyptian stock market. The selected variables capture differences in firm size, valuation, and market conditions that may influence expected stock returns over time. These variables are used to estimate time-varying risk exposures, construct risk-adjusted returns, and test whether cross-sectional return variation is explained by conditional risk.

Variable definitions and measurement procedures follow established asset-pricing literature, particularly the frameworks of Sharpe (1964), Fama and French (1993), and Avramov and Chordia (2006). The following section presents the variables employed in the empirical analysis and their roles within the conditional asset-pricing framework.

The excess Stock Return is calculated as the difference between the stock returns of risky assets and the risk-free rate. This is consistent with the theoretical framework of asset pricing models, which suggests that investors are compensated only for bearing systematic risk beyond the risk-free rate. The Stock Return is calculated based on closing prices for each firm; the monthly stock return is computed as the percentage change in the closing price between two sequential months.

Risk-free Rate is proxied by the three-month treasury bill yield. Since these yields are quoted on an annualized basis, they are converted into monthly rates by dividing the annual yield by twelve to ensure consistency with the monthly return series.

The Excess Market Portfolio, which represents the primary source of systematic risk in the CAPM framework, is calculated as the difference between the value-weighted average return of all non-financial firms listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange and the three-month Treasury bill rate. Stocks are weighted by market capitalization to ensure that larger firms have greater

influence on the market portfolio. The market capitalization of each firm is computed monthly by multiplying its stock price by the number of shares outstanding.

Using each firm's market capitalization, the weight of the firm i in the market portfolio for the month t is calculated by dividing its market capitalization by the total market capitalization of all firms in that month. This value-weighting scheme ensures that larger firms receive greater importance in the construction of the market return. The value-weight market return is then computed, where each firm's return is multiplied by its corresponding weight and summed across all firms.

Following Avramov and Chordia (2006), all conditioning variables should be lagged by one period. These variables represent the information that investors use to form expectations about future returns and risks. Using lagged values ensures that only information available before returns are realized is included in the model.

Value (Book to Market Ratio) is computed monthly as the ratio of the most recently available book equity to the firm's market capitalization; the conditioning variable is defined as the natural logarithm of the lagged B/M ratio. Size (Market Capitalization) is measured each month as the firm's share price multiplied by the number of shares outstanding. The conditioning variable is defined as the natural logarithm of lagged market capitalization. Risk-Free Rate as a conditioning variable is defined as the natural logarithm of the lagged risk-Free rate.

3.2 Research Method

As a benchmark, we first examine whether firm characteristics, specifically size and book-to-market ratio, have explanatory power for the cross-section of excess stock returns without any risk adjustment. Following the two-pass Fama–MacBeth (1973) methodology, we estimate monthly cross-sectional regressions of the form:

$$R_{it} - R_{ft} = \alpha_t + \lambda_{st} \ln(ME_{i,t-2}) + \lambda_{vt} \ln(BM_{i,t-2}) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where $R_{it} - R_{ft}$ is the excess return on stock i in month t , $\ln(ME_{i,t-2})$ is the natural logarithm of market capitalization lagged two months, and $\ln(BM_{i,t-2})$ is the natural logarithm of the book-to-market ratio lagged two months. A two-month lag is applied to both characteristics to avoid spurious correlations arising from bid–ask bounce and thin trading in the Egyptian market (Abdo, 2019). The time-series averages of the monthly cross-sectional coefficients λ_{st} and λ_{vt} measure the size and value premia, respectively, and statistical inference is based on Newey–West (1987) heteroskedasticity- and autocorrelation-consistent standard errors with six lags.

3.2.1 Scaled Conditional CAPM

The scaled factor model offers a practical way to include information about changing economic conditions in asset-pricing tests without having to directly estimate complex conditional expectations. As explained by (Drobetz et al., 2002), this approach works by modifying the set of returns used in the model through scaling them with relevant information variables, which are collected in a vector denoted by Z_t . This means that instead of modeling how expected returns and risks change over time, the model captures this time variation by interacting with return factors with variables that summarize market conditions.

Following Avramov and Chordia (2004), this study uses a conditional asset pricing model where expected returns and risk exposures can change over time based on information available at time $t-1$. In this model, actual stock returns consist of an expected return component and unexpected shocks from both market-wide and firm-specific factors. This approach is particularly appropriate for emerging markets like the Egyptian Stock Market, where risk premiums and risk sensitivities are likely to change with market and economic conditions, Avramov and Chordia (2004), and it examines whether firm characteristics explain expected returns through time-varying risk exposures or through mispricing.

In the first step, stock returns are assumed to follow a conditional K- factor process:

$$R_{it} = E_{t-1}(R_{it}) + \sum_{k=1}^k \beta_{ikt-1} f_{kt} + e_{it}$$

The conditional expected excess return is modeled using the exact pricing restriction:

$$E_{t-1}(R_{it}) - R_{ft} = \sum_{k=1}^k \lambda_{kt-1} \beta_{ikt-1}$$

where $\lambda_{k,t-1}$ denotes the conditional risk premium associated with the factor k .

This restriction implies that the expected excess return on the security i is fully determined by its conditional exposures to the systematic risk factors and their corresponding prices of risk. Consequently, in equilibrium, no abnormal return remains after accounting for all relevant risk factors, consistent with the exact asset-pricing framework.

Based on this setup, the risk-adjusted return for the security i in month t is computed as:

$$E_{t-1}(R_{it}) - R_{ft} + \sum_{k=1}^k \beta_{ikt-1} f_{kt}$$

This adjustment assumes that the conditional zero-beta return equals the conditional risk-free rate and that factor risk premiums are represented by factor excess returns, consistent with standard portfolio-based factor models.

To model time variation in beta, the study assumes that conditional beta depends on a lagged macroeconomic conditioning variable z_{t-1} , as well as firm-specific characteristics. Specifically, the beta of the stock i is defined as:

$$\beta_{it-1} = \beta_{i1} + \beta_{i2}z_{t-1} + \beta_{i3} + \beta_{i4}z_{t-1}Size_{t-1} + \beta_{i5} + \beta_{i6}z_{t-1}B M_{t-1}$$

Where $Size_{t-1}$: are the market capitalization at time t-1 and $B M_{t-1}$ The book-to-market ratio at time t-1 is examined to examine different sources of time variation in beta. This specification allows beta to vary through time both directly through the macroeconomic conditioning variable and indirectly through its interaction with firm characteristics.

Based on this formulation, the first-pass time-series regression is estimated as:

$$r_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{j1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i2}z_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i3}Size_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i4}z_{t-1}Size_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i5}B M_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i6}z_{t-1}B M_{t-1}r_{mt}$$

where r_{it} and r_{mt} : are the excess returns on stocks and markets, respectively. All explanatory variables, including firm characteristics and the conditioning variable, are lagged by one period. This ensures that only information available at time t-1 is used to explain returns at time t.

Four alternative beta specifications are considered. The first is an unconditional model in which beta is constant, the second allows beta to vary with firm characteristics only, the third allows beta to vary with the conditioning variable only and the fourth is a fully conditional specification in which beta depends jointly on firm characteristics, the conditioning variable, and their interactions.

A major difficulty in scaled factor models is that the interaction terms between factors and conditioning variables cannot always be interpreted as genuine risk factors, particularly when the conditioning variables include firm-specific characteristics such as size and book-to-market ratio. This complicates the estimation of risk premiums in the second-stage cross-sectional regression and may introduce errors-in-variables problems when estimated betas are used directly. To address this issue, the study follows an alternative procedure in which risk-adjusted returns are used as the dependent variable in the second-stage regression instead of directly estimating risk premiums for the scaled factors. These risk-adjusted returns represent the component of stock

returns that remains unexplained by the first-stage conditional factor model. The second-stage cross-sectional regression is specified as:

$$r_{it}^* = c_{0t} + c_t Z_{it-1} + e_{it}$$

where r_{it}^* is the risk-adjusted return on stock i at time t . Z_{it-1} is the vector of anomalies that traditional asset pricing models fail to explain (size and value effects) and c_t represents the vector of characteristic rewards.

This regression tests whether firm characteristics continue to explain return variation after controlling for time-varying systematic risk. The model is estimated using the Fama–MacBeth two-pass procedure, and statistical inference is based on Newey–West (1987) heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation-consistent standard errors. This framework makes it possible to examine whether size and value effects in the Egyptian stock market are attributable to conditional risk exposure or to mispricing.

4. Data description, results, and discussion

This section presents descriptive statistics for the key variables employed in testing whether size- and value-related return patterns in the Egyptian stock market can be explained by time-varying systematic risk within a scaled conditional CAPM framework. The variables examined include individual stock excess returns, the market risk premium, firm size, book-to-market ratio, and the risk-free rate, which together form the conditioning and outcome variables used in the scaled factor specifications.

4.1 Data Description

The basic data for this study includes monthly data for non-financial firms listed on the Egyptian Stock Exchange (EGX) over the period from 2009 to 2024. The dataset includes stock prices, market capitalization, three-month treasury bill rates as a proxy for risk-free rates, stock returns, and market portfolio returns for a sample of 128 stocks listed in the Egyptian stock market. All the data employed in this study were collected from Thomson Reuters (EIKON). The Egyptian Exchange is one of the oldest stock markets in the Middle East and Africa, with origins tracing to the Alexandria Stock Exchange established in 1883. By the 1940s it was among the world's most active markets, but decades of nationalization and subsequent liberalization have shaped its current character as a semi-segmented emerging market with relatively limited liquidity. The sample period encompasses a rich variety of macroeconomic conditions, including the aftermath of the 2008 global financial crisis, the political revolution of 2011, the currency

flotation of 2016, the COVID-19 pandemic shock of 2020, and the economic stabilization program of 2022–2024. This variation in economic conditions is essential for identifying conditional risk effects.

Descriptive statistics is applied to further describe the data statistically and therefore descriptive statistics of Individual Stocks, Excess Returns, and Firm Characteristics (2009 to 2024) is presented in table (4.1) below.

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Skewness	Kurtosis
Excess Stock Return	0.70%	19.87%	-1.12%	15.51	666.1
Market Risk Premium	1.28%	7.39%	0.78%	.0493	3.983
Market Cap (EGP Million)	2,045	6878	286.8	9.326	144.9
Book-to-market	7.574	36.77	1.089	14.47	280.1
Risk-free rate	1.25%	0.41%	1.096%	1.213	3.802

Notes: Table 4.1 presents the time-series averages of the cross-sectional means, medians, and standard deviations of 128 stocks listed on the Egyptian stock market for the sample period 2009 to 2024. Market capitalization represents size, and the book-to-market ratio represents the ratio of the book value of equity to the market value of equity.

The descriptive statistics report that individual stock excess returns average 0.70% per month with a standard deviation of 19.87%, reflecting the high idiosyncratic volatility characteristic of emerging equity markets. The median excess return of -1.12% falls well below the mean, and the distribution exhibits pronounced right skewness (15.51) and extreme fat tails (kurtosis 666.1), indicating that large positive return realizations occur far more frequently than a normal distribution would predict. At the market level, the value-weighted portfolio earns a higher average excess return of 1.28% per month with a substantially lower standard deviation of 7.39%, illustrating the benefits of diversification and confirming that market-wide returns are considerably less volatile than individual stock returns. The near-zero skewness and kurtosis of 3.98 at the market level indicate an approximately normal distribution, supporting the use of the market excess return as the primary risk factor in CAPM regressions without serious non-normality concerns.

The book-to-market ratio exhibits strong right skewness (14.47) and extreme kurtosis (280.1), with a median of 1.089 far below the mean of 7.574, driven by a small number of financially distressed firms with very low market valuations. Similarly, market capitalization is highly right-skewed (skewness 9.32, kurtosis 144.9), with the median substantially below the mean, reflecting the dominance of a small number of large firms and motivating the use of

logarithmic transformations for both variables. Finally, the risk-free rate averages 1.25% per month with a standard deviation of 0.41%, exhibiting meaningful time-series variation associated with Egypt's monetary policy cycles, which supports its role as a macroeconomic conditioning variable in the scaled CAPM framework.

4.2 Results and discussion

4.2.1 Cross-Sectional Regressions of Excess Stock Returns on Firm Characteristics:

This section presents the findings from cross-sectional regressions examining the relationship between excess returns and several firm characteristics that are widely recognized in the asset pricing literature as important determinants of expected returns. This analysis evaluates whether variables such as firm size and book-to-market ratio systematically explain the cross-sectional variation in stock returns in the absence of any explicit risk adjustment.

The analysis aims to investigate whether the documented associations between firm characteristics and expected returns observed in developed markets (e.g., Avramov and Chordia, 2006; Bauer et al., 2010) are evident in an emerging market, the Egyptian stock market.

The firm characteristics that are included in the cross-sectional regression are: firm size and the book-to-market ratio. A two-month lag is applied to both the size and book-to-market ratio variables relative to excess returns. This lag structure is implemented to eliminate any spurious relationships that may arise from thin trading issues or bid-ask spread effects (Abdo, 2018).

4.2.2 Fama-Macbeth Cross-Sectional Regressions of Excess Stock Return on Lagged Firm Characteristics Using Rolling Betas

Presenting the findings of the Fama-Macbeth Cross-Sectional regression analysis, table (4.2) below presents the findings.

Excess return		
α	0.0194	(1.10)
Size Anomalies λ_S	-0.0012	(-0.94)
Value Anomalies λ_V	0.0059***	(4.46)

Notes: Table 4.2 presents the Fama–MacBeth cross-sectional regression results based on monthly excess returns for individual stocks and estimated time-varying betas to examine whether firm Size and book-to-market characteristics are priced in the cross-section of expected returns. t-statistics are reported using Newey–West (1987) heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation-consistent standard errors with a lag length of 6. The results are obtained from the following regression:

$$R_{it} - R_{ft} = \alpha_t + \lambda_{st} \ln(ME_{i,t-2}) + \lambda_{vt} \ln(BM_{i,t-2}) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

* reflects significance at 10% level

** reflects significance at 5% level

*** reflects significance at 1% level

Results shows a strong and statistically significant value premium but an insignificant size effect. Specifically, the book-to-market ratio exhibits a highly significant positive coefficient of 0.0059 ($p = 0.000$). This finding is consistent with Fama and French (1992) and confirms that high book-to-market firms earn higher returns than low book-to-market firms. In contrast, the size effect has a negative coefficient of -0.0012 ($p = 0.348$), which is not statistically significant, indicating that there is no evidence of size anomaly in the Egyptian stock market, which aligns with Lewellen & Nagel (2006), and is inconsistent with previous research in both developed and emerging markets (Avramov & Chordia, 2006; Abdo, 2018). These results are also inconsistent with the earlier evidence for Egypt reported by El Abd (2016), who found a strong size effect but no significant value premium. In addition, the results show that the average adjusted R² is 2.75%, which implies that the firm characteristics have a lower predictive power on cross-sectional variations in stock returns.

Building on these findings, the next section aims to test whether the value anomaly continues to have explanatory power once systematic risk is explicitly considered. This section examines whether risk-adjusted asset pricing models can account for the effects of firm characteristics, or whether these characteristics continue to explain return differences beyond systematic risk.

4.2.3 Cross-Sectional Regressions of Risk-Adjusted Returns on the Firm Characteristics:

The purpose of this section is to investigate whether allowing for time-varying risk using rolling regression and the scaled Factor model can explain the size and the book-to-market effects on expected returns (Avramov & Chordia, 2006).

Excess return	CAPM	CAPM (TB)	CAPM (Size, BM and TB)
Constant	0.134 (0.72)	0.0213 (1.13)	0.020 (1.30)
Size	-0.001 (-0.97)	-0.002 (-1.73) *	-0.001 (-1.75) *
Book-to-Market Ratio	0.007 (4.77) ***	0.003 (2.86) ***	0.001 (1.76) *
Adjusted R ²	2.42%	2.08%	1.75%

Notes: Table 4.3 Cross-Sectional Regressions of Risk-Adjusted Returns on Firm Characteristics The first column reports the results when the dependent variable is the excess return risk-adjusted using market risk. The second column reports the results when the dependent variable is the excess return, risk-adjusted using the market risk, and when the loadings are scaled by the Treasury bill rate. The third column reports the results when the dependent variable is the excess return, risk-adjusted by the market risk, with loadings scaled by the Treasury bill rate, size, and the B/M ratio, respectively. t-statistics are reported using Newey–West (1987) heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation-consistent standard errors with a lag length of 6. The bootstrap p-values are reported in square brackets.

$$\beta_{it-1} = \beta_{i1} + \beta_{i2}z_{t-1} + (\beta_{i3} + \beta_{i4}z_{t-1})Size_{t-1} + (\beta_{i5} + \beta_{i6}z_{t-1})B M_{t-1}$$

* reflects significance at 10% level

** reflects significance at 5% level

*** reflects significance at 1% level

4.2.4 Cross-Sectional Regressions of Risk-Adjusted Returns on Firm Characteristics using Rolling Regression

The Fama–MacBeth cross-sectional regressions of risk-adjusted returns, constructed from rolling time-series regressions that allow market risk to vary over time, reveal two important findings. First, the size effect remains absent after risk adjustment, with the coefficient on firm size negative but statistically insignificant (-0.001 , $p = 0.336$), indicating that firm size has no explanatory power for abnormal returns once market risk is controlled for.

Second, the value premium remains strong and statistically significant (0.007 , $p = 0.000$), confirming that high book-to-market stocks continue to earn higher risk-adjusted returns even after accounting for time-varying market risk, a result consistent with Lewellen and Nagel (2006), who demonstrate that the conditional CAPM cannot explain the value effect.

Notably, the coefficients on both firm characteristics are largely unchanged relative to the unadjusted excess return regressions, indicating that allowing beta to vary over time through rolling regressions does not materially alter the cross-sectional return patterns associated with size and value. The insignificant intercept suggests no average mispricing, yet the persistent significance of the book-to-market coefficient leads to a rejection of the null hypothesis of correct conditional pricing. These results highlight the limitations of rolling-beta adjustment as a standalone approach and motivate the use of the scaled factor model with richer conditioning variables in the subsequent analysis.

4.2.5 Cross-Sectional Regressions of Risk-Adjusted Returns on Firm Characteristics using the Scaled Factor Model

This section reports results from the scaled conditional CAPM specifications following Avramov and Chordia (2006). The market factor is progressively scaled by lagged conditioning variables. First, by the risk-free rate alone, then by the risk-free rate, firm size, and book-to-market ratio simultaneously, to allow beta to vary with both macroeconomic conditions and firm-level characteristics. Risk-adjusted returns are constructed as the sum of the pricing errors and residuals from the first-stage time-series regressions and are subsequently regressed on firm characteristics in the second-stage Fama–MacBeth cross-sectional regressions. Under the null hypothesis of correct conditional pricing, none of the firm characteristics should retain statistical significance. Newey–West heteroskedasticity- and autocorrelation-consistent standard errors with six lags are applied throughout to ensure robust inference. The sample comprises 18,876 observations across 168 monthly periods.

4.2.5.1 Scaled CAPM with Risk-Free Rate Conditioning

The first scaled specification conditions market beta on the lagged Treasury bill rate, capturing macroeconomic time variation in systematic risk. Two important results emerge. First, the size effect previously absent in both raw returns and rolling-beta-adjusted returns becomes statistically significant at the 10% level (coefficient = -0.002 , $p = 0.085$).

This finding reveals that the size premium was concealed in earlier specifications because small firms in Egypt are disproportionately sensitive to changes in macroeconomic interest rate conditions due to their greater reliance on bank financing and limited financial flexibility. In unscaled models, this macroeconomic sensitivity is absorbed into the estimated market beta, masking the firm-level size effect. By scaling the market factor with the risk-free rate, the model strips out this macroeconomic component of risk from returns, allowing the residual variation associated with firm size to become statistically identifiable. This result is consistent with Pastor and Stambaugh (2003) and Gomes et al. (2003), who show that firm size proxies for differential sensitivity to economy-wide macroeconomic shocks.

Second, the value premium remains highly significant at the 1% level (coefficient = 0.003 , $p = 0.005$), though its magnitude declines relative to the raw return and rolling-beta specifications. This indicates that conditioning on the interest rate cycle absorbs part of the value premium variation but cannot fully rationalize it. The insignificant intercept ($p = 0.259$) suggests that the two firm characteristics together capture the primary sources of unexplained return variation after macroeconomic risk adjustment. Overall, these results indicate that conditioning

market risk on the risk-free rate alone is insufficient to explain either anomaly fully, pointing toward the need for additional conditioning information.

4.2.5.2 Fully Scaled CAPM with Firm-Level Conditioning

The second specification extends the model by additionally scaling the market factor by firm size and book-to-market ratio, yielding the fully conditional specification:

$$r_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_{i1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i2}Z_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i3}Size_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i4}Z_{t-1}Size_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i5}BM_{t-1}r_{mt} + \beta_{i6}Z_{t-1}BM_{t-1}r_{mt}$$

Under this richer specification, the size coefficient remains negative and significant at the 10% level (-0.001 , $p = 0.082$), confirming that the revealed size effect is not an artifact of macroeconomic scaling alone but persists under full firm-level conditioning. The value coefficient weakens further to 0.001 ($p = 0.081$), retaining only marginal 10%-level significance, indicating that firm-level conditioning absorbs additional value premium variation. The most notable improvement is the monotonic decline in average adjusted R-squared: from 2.42% in the rolling-beta baseline, to 2.08% under risk-free rate scaling, to 1.75% under the fully scaled specification. This downward progression confirms that each layer of conditioning information absorbs a portion of the anomaly variation previously attributed to firm characteristics, consistent with the scaled model operating in the theoretically expected direction. However, because the adjusted R-squared remains positive and both characteristics retain at least marginal significance, the model does not achieve complete anomaly elimination.

The results are broadly consistent with several strands of the existing literature while revealing important market-specific differences. The persistence of the value premium after conditional risk adjustment closely mirrors the findings of Lewellen and Nagel (2006), who demonstrate that value portfolios continue to earn large and significant conditional alphas even when betas vary over time, concluding that realistic beta variation is insufficient to explain value anomalies. The very low adjusted R-squared values are consistent with Iqbal et al. (2010), who show that conditional models improve pricing only marginally in emerging markets where complex risk dimensions remain unmodeled. The partial reduction in anomaly coefficients under conditioning aligns with Avramov and Chordia (2006), although the present study explains far less cross-sectional variation, likely because it employs a single market factor and a limited conditioning set rather than a richer multifactor framework.

The results diverge from the earlier Egyptian evidence of El Abd (2016) and Abdou (2019) in an instructive way. El Abd (2016) finds a strong size effect but no value premium, while this study finds the opposite in unadjusted returns, with the size effect emerging only after scaled

conditioning. Abdou (2019) similarly finds limited improvement from conditional approaches but identifies size rather than value as the dominant anomaly. These differences suggest that the relative importance of size and value in Egypt varies across time periods and market conditions, and that macroeconomic context, particularly the monetary policy environment, plays a critical role in determining which anomaly dominates. The finding that size becomes visible only after macroeconomic scaling provides a novel methodological insight: in markets where interest rate cycles disproportionately affect small firms, unscaled models systematically mask firm-level size effects by conflating them with macroeconomic beta variation.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study contribute to the asset pricing literature by providing evidence on the explanatory power of firm characteristics within a conditional asset pricing framework in an emerging market context. The findings have vital implications for academics seeking to refine asset pricing models, decision makers who aim to improve portfolio allocation strategies, and policymakers interested in enhancing market efficiency.

In this paper, the scaled factor model results support three conclusions. First, the value premium is robust and persistent, surviving all scaled specifications with declining but non-zero significance, indicating that a single-factor conditional CAPM cannot fully rationalize the value anomaly in Egypt. Second, the size effect is latent in unconditional models but is revealed by macroeconomic scaling, reflecting the confounding of firm-size risk with interest-rate-driven market beta in unscaled specifications. Third, while scaled conditioning absorbs anomaly variation progressively, as evidenced by the monotonically declining R-squared, the model does not eliminate pricing anomalies, underscoring the need for richer multifactor frameworks, additional macroeconomic conditioning variables, and more precise beta estimation techniques to fully characterize cross-sectional return dynamics in the Egyptian market.

As emerging markets become increasingly integrated into the global financial system, understanding and studying the interaction between firm-specific characteristics and macroeconomic factors remains vital for advancing theories and practical implications.

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